

THE ROLE AND LEGAL BASIS OF SMALL BUSINESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS STRUCTURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7105806>

Abstract. *This article describes the development of entrepreneurial structures in our country, their role and prospects in the development of small business, which is considered its main and leading link.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, small business, product, market, service, family business, raw materials.*

РОЛЬ И ПРАВОВЫЕ ОСНОВЫ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА В РАЗВИТИИ БИЗНЕС-СТРУКТУР

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассказывается о развитии предпринимательских структур в нашей стране, их роли и перспективах в развитии малого бизнеса, который считается его основным и ведущим звеном.*

Ключевые слова: *предпринимательство, малый бизнес, товар, рынок, услуга, услуга, семейный бизнес, сырье.*

INTRODUCTION

Although the separate analysis of the system of entrepreneurial activity first began in the West, the multifaceted knowledge related to its essence and development was formed in the East and then promoted in the West, as evidenced by the above-mentioned evidence. Especially, they are expressed in the teachings that were formed in this direction and have their place in life.

In the conditions of the market economy, there is no other way for an entrepreneur to influence the consumer than to act in accordance with the interests of the consumer. But this does not mean that the entrepreneur should act in accordance with the interests of the consumer. The entrepreneur himself can form consumer demand, create new consumer needs (if a new product needed by the customer is created). Based on this, there are two ways of organizing business activities:

- the method of determining the consumer's interest;
- a method of "forced acceptance" of a new product or service to a consumer.

Thus, the main goal of an entrepreneur is to determine the need for a product in order to acquire its customers. An entrepreneur should take into account the following main factors when forming his customers:

- novelty of the product and its compatibility with the buyer;
- quality of goods or services;
- price of goods or services;
- degree of universality of the product;
- appearance of the product, its compliance with the customer's requirements;
- the possibility of using after-sales service services;
- compliance of the goods with accepted general or state standards;
- the attractiveness of advertising of goods and services, attracting the attention of the buyer, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The conclusion is that if the entrepreneur is an active subject from the point of view of social production, then the consumer plays an active role in terms of the entrepreneurial process itself, its effectiveness and content, and the entrepreneur cannot deny this factor. Entrepreneur's personal characteristics, abilities, opportunities and job qualities are the driving force of entrepreneurship. The entrepreneur's work qualities should be based on the following principles:

— firstly, the market finds its place in the economic system by analyzing the level of supply of goods and services;

— secondly, the readiness to create a personal production structure;

— thirdly, based on the results of marketing research, make preliminary business calculations;

— fourthly, the ability to direct the leadership in the implementation of the business project;

— fifth, to be the first to implement a new technical and technological idea and to use this idea in practice, to imagine what final result, products or services can be obtained from it.

Entrepreneurship is an independent activity of citizens aimed at obtaining personal income and profit. This activity is carried out on its own behalf, at the expense of its own property responsibility and the legal responsibility of a legal entity. An entrepreneur may engage in all economic activities not prohibited by law, including brokerage, sale, purchase, consulting, and dealing with securities. Entrepreneurship is an activity related to the use of funds to obtain income for personal and social benefit. This definition of entrepreneurship is distinguished by its detail. In this definition, it is emphasized that entrepreneurship is not only engaging in certain activities, but also direct activities. A number of definitions given to entrepreneurship do not show the most important situation, that is, the integrity of personal income and social benefit.

RESULTS

Social, economic, legal and other specific conditions must be created for the formation of entrepreneurship. Economic conditions include: supply and demand for goods; availability of product types for the customer to purchase; the availability of the amount of money necessary for the buyer's purchase; surplus or shortage of jobs, labor force affecting the wages of workers, i.e. purchasing power. The availability of monetary resources and the possibilities of their use, the amount of income received from the invested capital and the amount of credit intended to be taken for financing one's business operations affect the economic conditions.

These activities are carried out by various organizations that have organized the market infrastructure. Entrepreneurs establish contact with such organizations and carry out commercial operations. Banks providing financial services, suppliers of raw materials, materials, semi-finished products, fuel, energy, machinery and equipment, instruments; wholesalers and retailers delivering goods to customers; firms and enterprises providing professional, legal, accounting services, mediation services; employment agencies that assist in the recruitment of labor; educational institutions training workers and specialist employees; advertising, transport, insurance agencies; means of communication and information transmission make up the system of these organizations. The formation of entrepreneurship is closely related to social and economic conditions. Social conditions are close to economic conditions of entrepreneurship formation.

Social conditions are primarily determined by the desire of customers to purchase goods that meet their taste and fashion. This requirement may change at different stages. This is

strongly influenced by moral and religious norms related to socio-cultural environment. These norms have a direct impact on the way of life of buyers and through it on the demand for goods. Social conditions affect the attitude of a person to work, which, in turn, affects the amount of salary offered by the business, and the attitude to working conditions.

It is important to solve the issues of training, retraining, and improving the skills of business employees in the formation of entrepreneurial activity. To do this, organize the study of modern methods of conducting business activities, train and retrain employees, send them to developed countries to improve their skills, organize training and retraining of teachers to train businessmen, for the entrepreneurship sector it is necessary to open counseling centers for the selection of employees. Every business activity takes place in an appropriate legal environment. Therefore, it is important to create the necessary legal conditions. First of all, it is the existence of decrees regulating business activities and legislation that creates favorable conditions for business development, that is, the process of registering enterprises is short and simple; protection of entrepreneurship from state bureaucracy; improvement of tax legislation; It consists in the development of cooperation between Uzbekistan and foreign businessmen. At the same time, this includes the organization of regional centers of assistance to small businesses, simplification of the statistical form and calculation. It is also important to solve the issues related to the issue of legal guarantee of business activity.

DISCUSSION

Proper organization of one's work is one of the main factors of entrepreneurship. That is why the entrepreneur should pay attention to all the parts that make up this phenomenon. When studying these aspects of an entrepreneur's activity, observing the process of his activity is of particular importance. In this case, the sequence of the main actions of the entrepreneur may be as follows:

- development of a business idea;
- in-depth study of the business environment;
- compatibility of the business idea with the entrepreneur's economic interest, compatibility of the business idea with the business environment;
- determining the necessary amount of capital for the implementation of the idea;
- formation of an enterprise or organization necessary for the implementation of a business idea.

Every entrepreneurial activity is based on a certain idea. These ideas are distinguished by their simplicity: someone comes up with the idea of packaging a product in a new way, introduces innovations to an existing product on the market, and tries to increase the level of demand for it on the basis of this, etc.

The idea of entrepreneurship often comes to people who are eager to gain independence and additional profit in their professional activities. For this, a person should analyze the economic processes in every way, identify the existing deficiencies in it, and direct his activities to it.

CONCLUSIONS

Entrepreneurship is defined as entrepreneurial activity carried out by legal entities and individuals on the basis of their own property responsibility, taking risks by producing products (providing services). Economic, political, social and legal conditions must be created for the formation and development of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship, as one of the forms of manifestation of social relations, not only helps to increase the potential of society, but also

creates a favorable ground for the manifestation of the abilities and skills of any person, helps to increase the national wealth and preserve the national spirit in the process of world integration. Therefore, the state pays great attention to the development of entrepreneurship and strengthening of its legal base.

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